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**An Ecospherical Approach to Forest in Janice Pariat's
*Everything the Light Touches***

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Abstract: *Janice Pariat's Everything the Light Touches is an extraordinary literary piece that concerns the perpetuity of nature in different time through the journeys of four different characters across different places. This paper is an attempt to address environmental problems resulted from the evolution of human society and human subjectivity, culture, politics and economy and the act of reduction of the natural resources for material environment by human beings. This paper has looked through the first episode of the novel that how human-nature relationship helps attaining abounding peace and happiness and man's preoccupation with forest and plant life can explore the astounding beauty and mystery of nature and its diverged aspects. Forest has occupied a considerable space in this episode as well as deforestation is a major concern undertaken by the central characters. Ecosophy demands a broad environmental awareness propagating the ideas about the requirements of our earth and our responsibilities to sustain it through reviewing our activities.*

Keywords: forest, deforestation, environment, ecosophy

Introduction:

The growing civilization, scientific and technical transmutation is a serious ecological crisis in present global scenario. The present generation has been edging out in collective mission of reduction and abstraction from nature for the cause of materialistic benefits, successes and worldly pleasures.

Anthropocentric and egotistical motives outrun the congenial relationship between human and other life forms. Norwegian philosopher Arne Naess and French philosopher Felix Guattari share the common concept of Ecosophy. The word ‘Ecosophy’ consists of two words similar like “Ecology” and both derived from Greek words. Ecosophy is a conjunction of ‘eco’ (oikos) - ‘home’ or in a larger concept our ‘earth’ and ‘sophy’ refers to ‘wisdom’. According to Levesque, “Ecosophy is a philosophical worldview or a system inspired by our living conditions in ecosphere.” (512) Karthick and Vaghese point out Arne Naess’ concept of ecosophy “which means through attaining ecological wisdom in one of the best ways to preserve and understand nature.” (128) Man’s awareness to environment and a cognitive realization to environmental issues, according to Guttari, is a needful process of “transformations of mentalities and collective habits” (Cavacante 26); otherwise our concern for material environment will be an illusion only. Moreover, Cavalcante construes Guttari’s concept of ecosophy in the following lines -

“Ecosophy is a practical and speculative model, ethical - political and aesthetic, not being a discipline, but rather a simple and efficient renewal of the old ways of conception of the human being, of society and of the environment.” (25)

Ecosophy is not a watertight philosophy; rather an active and progressive thinking on the dilapidated condition of nature and humans’ exploitative motives towards nature. It is an awareness on ecological destruction and man’s practical and realistic realization along with an attempt for constructive solutions that makes the basic footing of ecosophy. According to Cavalcante and Alves, “It proposes to analyze man in an integrative way of the environment in which he lives through the practical articulation of his daily life” (166). Therefore, ecosophy is a conception interlinking with critical thinking for the cause of interrelationship between environment , social relation and human subjectivity.

Analysis:

Recipient of Sahitya Akademi Young Writer Award for the English language in 2013 and Crossword Book Award for fiction in the same year; Janice Pariat is an Indian author and poet hailing from Northeast India. Her notable works include *Boats on Land, Seahorse, The Nine Chambered Heart, Everything the light Touches*. *Everything the Light Touches* won the Sushila Devi award for the best fiction in 2023 and short listed for JCB Prize for Literature in 2023. Her *She horse* was shortlisted for the Hindu Literary Prize in 2015. The present study has been limited to her latest fiction *Everything the Light Touches* - a seminal and ambitious work with a wide-ranging and deep-probing journeys through centuries.

Janice Pariat's *Everything the Light Touches* (2022) has featured four characters and they are Shai, Evelyn, Johann, and Carl. The characters have travelled across different centuries and continents touching everything tiny and mighty with a single liaison that the natural world is very close to us and breaking the relationship with earth means pulverizing our very spirits. Their travel encompasses from Northeast India's remote village to Lower Himalaya and Finland's Lapland to Gothe's Europe. The four characters have dived into a single passion for studying nature in a particular region and a geological period. The novel is centered round on ecological wisdom or ecosophy that human and natural world is intricately connected with each other with a radical spiritual bond.

Pariat is deeply concerned about the attenuated relationship of human and nature. Nature has been considered by human beings as utilizable resources and exploited arbitrarily for anthropocentric needs. The novel juxtaposes varied issues with a binary approach from colonial to modern, rural to urban, and capitalism to altruism. The novel begins with the vista of urbanization at the rural areas adjacent to Shillong -the capital of Meghalaya. Shai is a thirty two years old Khasi girl staying in Delhi and every homecoming of Shai explores expeditious urbanization in her hilly and cloud

shrouded region. Shai's home visit makes the picture more clear as she comes about to notice the rapid changes of landscape of her green hills. A deep ecosophic concern for ecoendangerment has been echoed throughout the feeling of Shai in the following lines-

Much of Shillong has been given over to manic construction, an inglorious clutter of unplanned cement structures-mostly illegal, of course, in an earthquake zone such as this. Every so often, the town is rattled by tremors, or a series of small rumbles. Warnings of what's to come, my mother likes to say, sounding as though she might even be wishing it upon us." (Pariat 11)

Shai's house is situated at the outskirts of Shillong and her parents live in a big house atop of a hill. Shai's father has nourished an especial interest in botany though by profession he is neither a teacher of botany nor an academician. He has been introduced in the novel as "Treeman of Shillong" (Pariat 20) - an environmental activist and lover of nature. He has begged some recognition to be an environmental protector and battler and his house is frequented by reporters. He has cultivated a deep passion for growing of plants, nourishment, and protection either from natural causes or humans. Pariat writes, - "Growing plants and saving them, from frost and aphids and too much rain." (Pariat 11). Shai's father is equally concerned on the growing deforestation in his region, "Especially when they might be felled. And "plant - bias"-our human tendency to underappreciate or ignore the flora around us -according to him, our species' gravest crime." (Pariat 11) Guattari is critique in his philosophical work *The Three Ecologies*, stating that man's overindulgent and imprudent challenge to the earth leads to ecocide. According to him, "After a century of unparalleled scientific and technological progress we have made our presence known to the planet in the most dramatic and self-defeating fashion." (Guattari 03)

The novel sets a pine forest that edges the small colony where Shai's house located. The pine forest covers the hills over and contributes to the greenery and beauty of the place. The novel

traces how Shai's father is anxious about the plan of cutting down a number of pine trees for the cause of construction of a wall by someone. The 'Treeman of Shillong' does not keep himself to be a silent observer of this felling activity of pine trees. However, he has approached to some forest officials accompanied by his comrade Bah Kyn with an appeal to stop the felling scheme of pine trees immediately.

Pariat has vivified the character of Shai's father by gifting him a plethora of botanical wisdom. The plants have evocative and communicative power like human and animal beings despite their immobility and lack of articulation capacity. This magical truth from scientific understanding has been put forth in the narrative through the botanical knowledge of Shai's father and the unknown mystery of plants and their "immense aromatic vocabulary, their capacity for memory." (Pariat 13) Shai's father alludes to birch tree when he gives to his daughter delightfully the most wonderful information about the remembering power of this plant in the following words- "Birch tree can remember a past event for up to four years." (Pariat 13) Shai has added her own comprehension saying that, "*All the trees in the world remember.*" (Pariat 14)

Nature affinity has been a serious and vital eco- theme delineated by Janice Pariat in her elegant novel *Everything the Light Touches*. *The Guardian* appreciates in the commentary pages of the novel remarking that "the natural world around us is loud enough for those willing to listen, and Pariat has found the language for it." (Pariat) Janice Pariat has depicted Shai's ecosophic self in the line of her father. Her eco-aesthetic virtue has been best understood when she sets her bed by the window in her living room of her house directing to the pine forest. She likes the forest and the natural music emitting out from the deep of the forest. She loves to listen "the chirrup of crickets, and from near the stream, a bright chorus of frogs." (Pariat 14) During her sojourn at home, Shai occasionally goes into the nearest forest to seek happiness after having been away from the bustling city life. She says, "I wish I could say I find peace here - or a joyous

communion--Perhaps the city has dulled my heart, my senses.” (Pariat18) She understands her incompetence to be attuned with her father’s passion for interacting with forest due to her professional obligation in the big city Delhi.

The novel delves deep into the ecosystem of plants through the botanical knowledge of Shai’s father. The world of trees on earth surface is not only the world we are visualizing. There is another world or a complicated wide network underneath the surface of our earth woven by the roots of the trees. Shai comes to know from her father the botanical term of this extensive network as “Hyphae” (Pariat 21) or network of fungus from root to root. Shai terms it in her simple understanding as “The wood wide web”. According to Wohlleben, “Life in these hidden ecosystems has barely been explored, and we only know about a tiny fraction of the species that live down here.” (46) This infinite biological phenomenon makes an underworld of trees. In this unseen world, trees make their intricate relationship among them and prepare a strong ecosystem sharing “resources, information, nutrients.” (Pariat 21)

Moreover, ecological balance has been seen more beautifully designed among the trees in the underworld; mutual support within the same kin and the role of caretaker by the healthy trees to the weaker ones provides throughout the web interconnected roots to roots. The trees, besides their generous role of life giver to other living beings, make a beautiful paragon of coexistent species. Shai expresses, “Others believes trees care for one another, and act as guardians, sharing resources, with the healthy supporting the weak. A free market versus a socialist’s dream.” (Pariat 21) Human beings, the most elite and wise among other beings, not only exploit within same kin but also others recklessly. The novel points out many ironical or superficial environmental awareness popped up in sociocultural practices rather than a realistic understanding. Guattari (qtd. in Cavalcante and Alves 168) states that -

Environmental Ecosophy aims to articulate new ecological practices. These new ecological practices must make the subjective singularities of humanity progressive and active, moving to collective thinking, in the well-being of the group. Thus, heterogeneity has the capacity to organize and articulate the functioning of the global system.

The first episode of *Shai in Pariate's Everything the Light Touches* finally turns out Shai's father to be a champion in the cause of forest. He involves in the environmental fight that issued forth from cutting of pine trees that has been inchoate for a wall construction. Finally the forest department interferes into the matter and a number of pine trees are saved from felling down. Shai's father is delighted that finally their efforts to save the pine trees do not go in vain. "The new wall, it has been mandated, will be slimmer. A victory for the Treeman of Shillong" (Pariat 54). Parait has shown throughout the character of Shai's father that ecosophy is a realistic approach and it is call for solidarity in shifting perspective that can foster a holistic understanding of human and nature.

Conclusion:

The study is an attempt at assessing the literary representation of forest in North East Indian writing in English. It has examined the forest and human relationship and the wonder and mystery in the world of plants from the ecohumanistic wisdom in Janice Pariat's *Everything the Light Touches*. Human beings have an ancient connection with forest since its Homo sapiens stage. The wheel of civilization and urbanization bring about a massive rift between the two and the deep affinity between the two entities has been dissipating day by day. According to the propagator of Deep Ecology Arne Naess the anthropocentric activities of human beings lead humans to live alienated from their natural environment" (Nayar 246). The insightful ecosophic awareness of non-anthropocentric attitudes must repair the growing crevice between man and nature. Moreover, nature

provides overflowing amount of joy and happiness to those who love living close to nature and understands its magnitude.

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